

A Journey to Identify Users' Classification Strategies to Customize Games and Gamified Environments

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I. TECHNICAL REPORT

THIS technical report presents a curated selection of publications that have undergone the second filtering stage in the systematic literature mapping (SLM) process.

Table I summarizes the aspects evaluated in this mapping, according to the four groups: (i) Classification strategies the publications adopt to customize/personalize game elements according to user profiles, (ii) the application context of such customization/personalization, (iii) the instruments frequently used to identify the users' profiles, and (iv) the application types.

A. Characteristics (Classification strategies)

Concerning the user characteristics that serve as the basis for the taxonomies, we mainly found interaction based profile, user personality, and learning motivation style. We found most publications used user interaction (28 publications). Users' personality was used in eight publications, followed by learning style in five publications and learning motivation style in one publication.

B. Context

Concerning the area where the gameful application is inserted, publications were applied to the educational, simulation, health, workout area, environmental behavior, and generic (other).

Education is the area that has received the most attention (25 publications), from language learning to higher education subjects. Subsequently, six publications were not applied to a specific area: two of them are proposals and validation of taxonomies, which can be used in any area, and one analyzes factors to be considered in gamification regardless of the application area. Exergames represent five publications. Studies in the health area represent 10% of the selected ones (4), followed by the areas of environmental behavior and simulation with a single publication.

C. Instruments

Concerning the instruments used to verify the effect of game elements on user profiles, publications adopted: (i) questionnaires (fifteen publications); (ii) log records (fourteen publications); and (iii) a combination of both (thirteen publications).

D. Application Type

Concerning the type of application (i.e., games, gamification, or both), although the search string contains the word "game", 37 publications (88.10%) concerned gamification, four (9.52%) concerned serious games, and only one (2.38%) proposes to be used in both, identified in Table I as gamification and serious games.

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TABLE I
CONSOLIDATION OF RESULTS.

User type Classification Strategies	Characteristics (Classification strategy)	User interaction	[1]–[30]
		User personality	[5], [24], [30]–[35]
		Learning style	[36]–[40]
		Motivation for learning	[41]
	Context	Education	[3], [6]–[10], [12], [14], [15], [19], [26]–[28], [31]–[33], [41], [42] [34]–[40]
		Simulation	[4]
		Environmental Behavior	[25]
		Generic	[1], [5], [13], [16], [22], [30]
		Health	[11], [18], [18], [20], [23]
		Workout	[2], [17], [21], [24], [29]
		Questionnaires	[1], [3], [5], [11], [13], [15]–[17], [20], [22], [23], [26], [27], [29], [42]
	Instruments	Log System	[4], [6]–[8], [14], [21], [24], [31]–[33], [35], [37], [41]
		Both	[2], [9], [10], [12], [18], [19], [25], [28], [30], [36], [38]–[40]
	Application types	Serious Games	[11], [31]–[33]
		Gamification	[1]–[3], [5]–[10], [12], [14], [15], [22], [23], [34]–[41] [4], [16]–[21], [24]–[30]
		Both	[13]

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